

The type 3 innate lymphoid cell (ILC3) in humans with Crohn's Disease.

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A complete description of the sequence of events that results in development of the inflammatory bowel diseases Crohn's Disease and ulcerative colitis has not yet been defined. Hematopoietic derived cells of the gut that are relevant to IBD initiation and IBD biology include regulatory T cells, Th17 cells, lamina propria cells of the gut, intraepithelial IEC, and innate lymphoid cells (ILC)) ILC1, ILC2 and ILC3. We provide here a brief description of the most distinguishing features of the ILC3 transcriptome in humans with Crohn's Disease. IBD-associated ILC3 purified based on CD45, CD127 and CD117 expression were CD2+, CD74+, CD38+, CD52+ and CD69+, CD59+ and CD48+. ILC3 displayed class II MHC receptors HLA-DRA, HLA-DPA1 and HLA-DMA but not MHC-I, expressed high levels of interferon stimulated genes including IFIT2, IFI44 and IFI6 as well as the inflammasome-associated guanylate binding proteins GBP3 and GBP5, expressed caspases CASP4 and CASP6 and the innate immune receptor PYCARD. ILC3 isolated from humans with Crohn's Disease expressed interleukins IL-18 and IL-15 and receptor subunits for the IL-11 and IL-13 cytokines. At the cell surface, inflammatory bowel disease-associated ILC3 were enriched for expression of TMEM128 and TMEM230 and TMEM9, GPR34 and GPR89A, and receptors AMIGO2, VSIG1 and PILRA. ILC3 from humans with Crohn's Disease rearranged or activated TCR delta constant region and joining genes while silencing or repressed TCR alpha and beta gene expression. Nuclear factor expression included *THEMIS* and *IKZF3*; the inflammatory bowel disease-associated ILC3 expressed grancalcin and the natural killer activation marker NKG7.

References

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